

“Non Performing Assets: A Comparative Study of Sbi & Hdfc Bank”

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ABSTRACT:

Finance is used to accomplish the money of any business. Business would not be capable to run without finance and may not get release. Finance is the basically art & science of dealing funds of business concern is really crucial for the existence of business unit. Finance plays a significant role right from group business awareness to its day to day effective insolvency stage of business. Finance aids in obtaining various researcher such as raw material, machinery & equipment, human resources etc. and it help to keep the smooth flow of business process. Financial management organization in an association is important in simple words we can say that finance is a blood of business.

Keywords: Comparative Study, Ratio Analysis, Financial Management, NPA

I.INTRODUCTION:

A robust banking sector is very significant for a healthy economy. One in the every of the foremost vital and major roles contended by the banking sector is that of loaning business. It is usually inspired as result of funds being transferred from the system to productive functions that conjointly result in the economic process. As there are a unit execs and cons of everything constant is with loaning business that carries credit risk that arises from the failure of the receiver to satisfy its written agreement obligation either throughout the course of dealing or on a future obligation. The failure of

banking sector could have associate in a nursing adverse impact on different sectors. Now playing assets area unit one in each of the main consideration for banks in India.

Banking:

Bank is a financial institution that is licensed to deal with money and its substitute by accepting time and demand deposits, making loan & investing in securities. The bank generates profits from the difference in the interest rates charged and paid. The development of banking is an inevitable precondition for the healthy and rapid development of the national economic structure. Banking institution have contributed much to the developed countries of the world. Today we cannot imagine world without banking institutions. Banking is as important as blood in the human body. Due to the development of banking advances are increased and business activities developing so it is rightly said, “The development of banking is not only the root but also result of the development of business world.”

II.REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

A Study on NPA’s of select Public and Private Sector Banks in India aimed to examine and compare the Gross NPAs and Net NPAs of select Public and Private Sector Banks. Classified Indian private division banks on the premise of their monetary characteristics and analyzed their money related execution. They found that return on resources and interest wage have a negative relationship with operational productivity while, positive relationship with resource utilization and resource estimate.

Banking sector reforms and NPAs in Indian commercial banks to examine the trends of NPAs in India from various dimensions and to explain how immediate recognition and self-monitoring has been able to reduce it to a great extent.

(Bhatia 2007) in his research paper entitled, Non-performing assets of Indian public, private and foreign sector banks studied that, the NPAs are considered as an important parameter to judge the performance and financial health of banks. This aims to find the fundamental factors which impact NPAs of banks.

III.PURPOSE OF THE STUDY:

Banks can improve their financial position or can increase their income from credits with the help of this study.

To study can be used for comparing the performance of the Bank with other Bank.

To can also be applicable to know the reasons of increase in NPAs.

To study also gives light upon impact of NPAs on performance and profit of Bank

IV.RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The present study is based on secondary data analysis. The data has been collected from various web sources like annual reports of respective Banks, information bulletins and journals. The data collected were analyzed with the help of statistical tools like Ratio analysis, and trend analysis. Tables are used to represent the consolidated data. Graphical representation is also used for better comprehension & presentation

Here, NPA is the independent variable and net profit is the dependent variable. So we see if due to any changes in the net NPA, the net profits change or not, if yes, whether positively or negatively.

Indian banking industry, which was in glory phase once upon a time, has been facing a lots of Challenges non-performing assets at present scenario. Many banks have kept their NPAs Under the control but some banks are not able to control their NPA levels. They are facing lots of Problems. There can be various reasons behind this NPA. Non-performing assets has been hitting the profitability of the banks or it can be said that due to NPA, the profitability of the banks are going down day by day. The subsidiary for this is the functioning of Debt Recovery Tribunal (DRT) which is a judiciary for the bank for recovery amount from the default customers. These can be considered as a research problem based on which the information is collected, the object is measured and the data is analyzed and interpreted.

HYPOTHESES FORMULATION:

H1: There exists a relationship between NPAs and profitability of private banks.

H2: The recovery mechanisms adopted by private banks are effective.

In nutshell above literature review, it shows up that over the long time, different endeavors have been made by the analysts and academicians to assess the money related position and execution of open division Banks and private division Banks from diverse perspectives. But there's no seminal work made on the investigation of the NPAs of SBI and HDFC from open segment Banks and private segment Banks separately in India. So, the display consider has attempted to highlight this untouched zone.

V.DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRITATION

In the below section, various parameters related to NPA are compared and analyzed.

Firstly, the total advances, net profits, gross NPA and net NPAs have been compared for both the Banks.

YEAR	TOTAL ADVANCES		NET PROFIT		GROSS NPA		NET NPA	
	SBI	HDFC	SBI	HDFC	SBI	HDFC	SBI	HDFC
2015-16	1300026	365495.03	13102	10215.92	56725.34	3438.38	27590.58	896.28
2016-17	1463700	464593.96	9951	12296.21	98172.80	4392.83	55807.02	1320.37
2017-18	1571078	554568.2	10484	14549.64	112342.9	5885.66	58277.38	1843.99
2018-19	1934880	658333.09	-6547	17486.73	223427.4	8606.97	110854.7	2601.02

TOTAL ADVANCES:

NET PROFIT

1. GROSS NPA

NET NPA

Secondly, the examination of the NPA trends for both the Banks for the last 4 years has been done.

PERCENTAGE OF GROSS NPA

YEAR	PERCENTAGE OF GROSS NPA	
	SBI %	HDFC %
2015-16	4.25	1.30
2016-17	6.5	1.05
2017-18	9.11	0.94
2018-19	10.91	0.90

Capital Adequacy Ratio

Capital Adequacy Ratio can be defined as ratio of the capital of the Bank, to its assets, which are weighted/adjusted according to risk attached to them i.e.

Name of the Bank	Capital adequacy ratio
State Bank of India	13
HDFC Bank	15

Interpretation:

Each Bank needs to create the capital Reserve to compensate the Non- Performing Assets. Here, HDFC Bank has shown Better capital adequacy ratio with 15% as compare to SBI with 13%.So, we can say that HDFC Bank has much power than SBI to compensate for NPAs.

Provision Ratio:

Provisions are to be made for to keep safety against the NPA, & it directly effect on the gross profit of the Banks.

NAME OF BANK	PROVISION RATIO
SBI	65.95
HDFC	78.7

Provisions are to be made for to keep safety against the NPA, & it directly effect on the gross profit of the Banks.

Interpretation:

This Ratio indicates the degree of safety measures adopted by the Banks. It has direct bearing on the profitability; the highest provision ratio is showed by HDFC Bank with 78.7% as compared to State Bank of India with 65.95 %.

VI.FINDINGS:

The following findings were drawn from the above data analysis-

- SBI Bank shows high NPAs Ratio as compare to HDFC Bank.
- High NPAs Ratio shows low credit portfolio of SBI Bank.
- In analysis HDFC low risk profile as compare to SBI in terms of NPAs.
- Study also indicates that major NPA increases because of govt. recommended priority sectors.
- HDFC have better capital adequacy ratio than SBI.
- The total advances have shown an upwards trend for both SBI and HDFC Bank
- In the case of % Gross NPA, performance of Private sector Bank- HDFC is doing better as compared to Public sector Bank –SBI Bank

VII.CONCLUSION

To conclude this study we can say about this report, that SBI Bank shows very much high NPA ratios as compare to HDFC. NPAs represent high level of risk & low level of credit appraisal. There are some certain guidelines made by RBI for NPAs which are adopted by Banks. HDFC is better in all terms than SBI.

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